

Enabling Personalized Implant and Controllable Biosystem Development Through 3D Printing

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Abstract:

The impact of additive manufacturing in our lives has been increasing constantly. One of the frontiers in this change is the medical devices. 3D printing technologies not only enable the personalization of implantable devices with respect to patient-specific anatomy, pathology and biomechanical properties but they also provide new opportunities in related areas such as surgical education, minimally invasive diagnosis, medical research and disease models. In this review, we cover the recent clinical applications of 3D printing with a particular focus on implantable devices. The current technical bottlenecks in 3D printing in view of the needs in clinical applications are explained and recent advances to overcome these challenges are presented. 3D printing with cells (bioprinting); an exciting subfield of 3D printing, is covered in the context of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine and current developments in bioinks are discussed. Also emerging applications of bioprinting beyond health, such as biorobotics and soft robotics, are introduced. As the technical challenges related to printing rate, precision and cost are steadily being solved, it can be envisioned that 3D printers will become common on-site instruments in medical practice with the possibility of custom-made, on-demand implants and, eventually, tissue engineered organs with active parts developed with biorobotics techniques.

Keywords: Biomedical Devices, Personalized Medicine, Bioprinting, Biorobotics, Implants

41 1. Introduction:

42 Additive manufacturing has been slowly pervading to all aspects of life and is a driving force in a silent
43 revolution in how we design, develop and manufacture products. Since early 80s, following the footsteps
44 of the stereolithography breakthrough by Charles W. Hull, the advances in the production of 3D
45 structures with a wide range of technologies have been achieved that enabled the additive manufacturing
46 of different forms of materials. As a highly regulated domain, medicine has been, up to now, slow in
47 uptake of 3D printing technologies due to the particular restrictions in the materials that can be used.
48 However, as 3D printing field matured, technologies for printing clinically relevant materials with the
49 required precision have evolved (Murphy and Atala, 2014). Currently, there are dedicated instruments
50 that can print medical grade ceramics, metals and polymers for medical uses. There are many occasions
51 where 3D printed implants, although mostly anecdotal or in limited series, have been used clinically (Di
52 Prima et al., 2015). Also the availability of the technology has brought further innovations for the use
53 of 3D printed structures (such as surgical simulation). ASTM and ISO standards currently recognizes 7
54 processes for additive manufacturing all of which has been adapted for medical use to a certain extent:
55 These processes are: powder bed fusion, material extrusion, material jetting, binder jetting, sheet
56 lamination, direct energy deposition and vat photopolymerization (ISO). This wide range of available
57 technologies together with those under development provides a positive outlook for further
58 establishment of 3D printing techniques for biomedical devices field.

59 Still, the portion of medical devices in overall 3D market, which is on its way to become a multibillion
60 \$ market, is less than 5%. One of the biggest roadblocks that leads to this is the disruptive nature of 3D
61 printing technology; the methods used for 3D printing do not conform well with the processes developed
62 for validation and quality checks of medical devices in use. Establishing the necessary validation process
63 regarding customized 3D printed products (for example an instrument and non-invasive sampling based
64 validation process rather than implant lot based validation) is an important step that needs to be taken
65 together by the regulatory actors and industry. This is particularly crucial for bioprinting applications
66 for which the final products will be by default Class III products or ATMPs (Advanced Therapeutic
67 Medicinal Products) and thus have higher levels of regulatory constraints (where ISO standard 10993
68 for biocompatibility needs to be observed for example for both FDA approval and for obtaining CE
69 mark). Moreover, the patient-specific shape and architecture also complicate validation of certain design
70 parameters. For example, for a set implant design the mechanical failure analyses can be done via
71 simulation or experimentally but for a unique implant this needs to be repeated for each implant as the
72 specific shape based on anatomical constraints can weaken the overall structure. As preparing several
73 samples of each implant for each patient for just testing is untenable, reliable simulation-based
74 verification means needs to be implemented. However, this route has not been fully embraced by the
75 regulatory bodies yet. Moreover, most of the 3D printed structures will have intricate interior designs
76 which needs to be validated post-printing with non-invasive but robust methods, for example micro-CT
77 validation of interior dimension fidelity (Hollister et al., 2016). In addition, possible compromises with
78 the sterility can be also linked with the architectural differences between the implants and assuring the
79 sterility might require additional steps, which is not necessary for conventional implants. Readers are
80 referred to the cited reference which explains the difficulties and requirements of such validation
81 processes for a 3D printed tracheobronchial splint for pediatric use (Morrison et al., 2015b). However,
82 it should be noted that tracheobronchial splint has a well-defined reference design where several
83 parameters are changed to optimize the final implant for a specific patient. This will not be the case for
84 filling of defects or partial organ replacement, for example, and can further complicate the verification
85 and validation processes.

86 Also, there are significant logistics related problems particularly for ATMPs produced by 3D bioprinting
87 as the sourcing of the cells of the patient, the location of the printing and the fragile nature of the final
88 products require a tight synchronization of diagnosis, clinical decision, implantable structure production,
89 delivery and implantation. However, in the view of potential benefits for patients, healthcare system and
90 overall society, the required amount of work to achieve this is reasonable. Moreover, bioprinting driven
91 research in hydrogel 3D printing can have other overarching effects as recently demonstrated. Additive
92 manufacturing of hydrogels can be used for design and implementation of implantable
93 microelectromechanical systems where stimuli responsive hydrogels can function as barriers, valves,

94 pumps etc. (Zorlutuna et al., 2013). A recent elegant example demonstrates the potential of using 3D
95 printing for development of devices with soft controllable components. Using iron oxide nanoparticle
96 doped photopolymerisable poly(ethyleneglycol) diacrylate (PEGDA) hydrogels, Chin et al demonstrated
97 a wirelessly activated drug payload system that contains movable mechanical components for triggered
98 release(Chin et al., 2017) . This system was demonstrated to be effective in controlled delivery of
99 doxorubicin, a widely used anti-cancer drug, and shown to be efficient at concentrations 1/10th of that is
100 used in clinical practice.

101 In this review, we aim to provide a state of the art overview of the currently available bioprinting
102 techniques and bioink formulations that are under development. This will be followed by use of 3D
103 printing technologies for implantable devices with examples of clinical applications. Finally, the use of
104 bioprinted structures beyond medical devices and regenerative medicine with recent examples will be
105 introduced.

106

107 **2. Bioprinting Applications**

108 Bioprinting is the 3D printing of artificial tissues and organs by precisely assembling the cells and
109 natural or synthetic cell matrices, layer-by-layer to achieve highly accurate biomimetic
110 constructs(Mandrycky, Christian et al., 2016; Wu, Z. et al., 2016). Currently used conventional tissue
111 engineering techniques remain insufficient for fabricating completely functional, vascularized tissues
112 and organs(Ozbolat et al., 2016). In this regard, bioprinting techniques have enabled rapid development
113 of the structured organization of multiple cells, ECM molecules and growth factors that promote
114 vascularization and functionality in engineered tissue constructs(Gauvin et al., 2012; Jeong et al., 2012;
115 Zorlutuna et al., 2011). These biomimetic vascularized constructs have potential applications as tissue
116 implants(Murphy and Atala, 2014) and disease models(Ozbolat, 2015), for drug screening(Loessner et
117 al., 2010) and pharmaceutical discovery(Peng et al., 2016), as well as in stem cell research(Tasoglu and
118 Demirci, 2013). Commonly used bioprinting approaches for layer-by-layer deposition of live cells
119 include inkjet(Campbell and Weiss, 2007), extrusion(Ozbolat and Hospodiuk, 2016), laser (optical
120 trapping) (Guillotin et al., 2010), stereolithography(Chan et al., 2010) and acoustic(Gurkan et al., 2014)
121 based techniques. In this section, we provide a brief overview of the bioinks used in bioprinting, broad
122 applications of bioprinting in developing artificial tissue constructs for transplantation, building tissue
123 models for pharmaceuticals, and finally, current advances *in situ* bioprinting (Norotte et al., 2009).

124 **2.1 Bioinks:**

125 In tissues, cells are arranged into 3D structures and surrounded by extracellular matrix (ECM) molecules
126 such as collagen, glycosaminoglycans and proteoglycans. Apart from being an adhesive substrate, the
127 ECM regulates the cell communication, proliferation and the differentiation.

128 The great need for biocompatible bioinks mimicking the chemical and physical properties used in 3D
129 bioprinting technology has directed research efforts towards this field in the last decade. So far, a range
130 of natural polymers has been implemented and 3D printed with cells especially for tissue regeneration.
131 However only a few of them such as collagen(Kim, Y. B. et al., 2016), alginate(Chung et al., 2013;
132 Duan et al., 2013; Khalil and Sun, 2009; Markstedt et al., 2015), gelatin(Bertassoni et al., 2014;
133 Chameettachal et al., 2016; Du et al., 2015; Duan et al., 2013; Mandrycky, C. et al., 2016),
134 dextran(Pescosolido, L. et al., 2011), fibrin(Xu et al., 2013) and hyaluronic acid(Pescosolido, L. et al.,
135 2011) have received a common interest due to their biocompatibility, 3D printing fidelity and *in vivo*
136 biodegradability (Figure 1). Despite their advantages, many issues related to these biopolymers are still
137 needed to be addressed. For instance, some of the hydrogels prepared from collagen and hyaluronic acid
138 have difficulties when printed alone. For this reason, they need to be modified further or to be combined
139 with other biomaterials to be able to control their rheological properties and printability. Furthermore
140 the weak mechanical properties of such natural polymers limits their applications in bioprinting.

141 The use of hydrogels with appropriate properties (e.g. shear thinning, thickening, yield stress) in the 3D
142 printers has been shown to be ideal to build-up hierarchical scaffolds. Both natural and synthetic

143 polymers have been used in various 3D printing applications (Figure 1). Although some of the synthetic
144 polymers are useful in terms of printability (e.g. easy gelation after printing, less degradation and
145 operation advantage under various conditions), the natural biopolymers mimic the ECM conditions more
146 suitably. A hydrogel can be formed by cross-linking of the polymer chains. The cross-linking occurs
147 either via chemical or physical interaction. The chemical cross-linking is irreversible where the polymer
148 chains are locked covalently. The physical interactions can be controlled as a function of pH, ionic
149 strength and temperature *etc.*

150 An ideal bioink must demonstrate a shear thinning behavior which allows a continuous flow and
151 printability under a high shear rate. When the shear rate increased, the viscosity of the bioink decreases
152 due to the rearrangement of the bioink components into aligned form. When the shear force is withdrawn
153 the viscosity increases again resulting a more solid-like gel. This is a typical feature of a hydrogel that
154 allows for printing under shear force, which is a pressure in many cases, and shape retaining after
155 printing. The shear thinning behavior of silk fibroin gels as a function of applied shear rate has been
156 demonstrated previously.(Ghosh et al., 2008) Although the gels with relatively high viscosity improves
157 the printability, longer printing times and the risk of cell death requires novel bioinks with low-viscosity.
158 A low-viscosity bioink composed of alginate and gelatin methacryl (GelMA) has been shown
159 previously.(Colosi et al., 2016) GelMA was used for cell encapsulation due to its ability to form a
160 chemically stable hydrogel when exposed to UV light compared to ionically crosslinked alginate. One
161 of the most important property of a hydrogel used as bioink is to support cell viability by surrounding
162 the soft cell aggregates. The viscosity of the hydrogel plays a significant role on the cell viability. The
163 low viscosity bioinks are more suitable for cell viability, however their printability and cross-linking
164 capacity are low in most cases. Catros et al. have studied the influence of bioink viscosity on the viability
165 of endothelial cells. The results have showed that increasing bioink viscosity of alginate improves cell
166 viability after Laser-Assisted Bioprinting.(Catros et al., 2011) The use of more gel-like biopolymers
167 such as a semi-interpenetrating network (semi-IPN) could improve the cell viability due to the moderate
168 interaction between the cells and the polymer network. Pescosolido et al. have demonstrated a novel 3D
169 hydrogel bioprinted construct of semi-IPN, based on hyaluronic acid and hydroxyethyl-methacrylate-
170 derivatized dextran (dex-HEMA) with improved chondrocyte viability(Pescosolido, Laura et al., 2011).
171 Recent developments in supramolecular chemistry have facilitated the design of novel bioinks with
172 tailored properties eliminating prolonged recovery times in cross-linking. Such systems include a new
173 class of HA hydrogels that form through specific noncovalent guest–host interactions and self-heal
174 rapidly when shear forces are removed(Loebel et al., 2017) and self-assembled peptide-based hydrogels
175 (Raphael et al., 2017).

176 Although bioink-based scaffolds support the cells to approach biological and mechanical properties of
177 the tissue constructs, the migration and reorganization of the cells in such scaffolds might be problematic
178 due to stress factors. Moreover, such scaffolds might require relatively strong cross-linkers and generate
179 immunogenic and toxic degradation by-products which influence the cell survival. Recently, the
180 scaffold-free bioinks, using directly cells or cell-aggregates in bioprinting process, have taken attention
181 due to its ability to fabricate 3D artificial tissue constructs without any support materials. A cell sheet-
182 based bioink preparation method was demonstrated in which the cells were proliferated on poly(N-
183 isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAAm) coated surfaces and then were used as a bioink for 3D bioprinting.
184 (Bakirci et al., 2017) In addition, a method in which the cellular components of a tissue are removed to
185 form a decellularized ECM bioink (dECM) by the physical, chemical and enzymatic processes has been
186 recently developed. The 3D Bioprinting is performed with this material containing encapsulated living
187 stem cells. This was followed by direct incubation of the printed construct for gelation (establishing
188 structural integrity). Thus the individual components and unique complexity of the natural ECM is
189 represented entirely in the final biomimetic construct. A high cell viability and functionality of the
190 dECM bioinks including adipose, cartilage and heart tissues have been achieved using this approach
191 (Pati et al., 2014). For an extensive list of available bioinks, the readers are referred to a recent review
192 dedicated to bioinks(Hospodiuk et al., 2017).

193

194 **Figure 1.** 3D Bioprinted constructs of various bioinks. A) A 3D grid printed using collagen-based
195 bioink mixed with cell culture medium. The structure is reinforced with genipin crosslinking. Scale bar

196 3 mm(Kim, Yong Bok et al., 2016). B) 3D printed hyaluronic acid, for reinforcement a
197 photocrosslinkable dextran derivative was incorporated to the bioink for obtaining semi interpenetrating
198 networks (Pescosolido, Laura et al., 2011) C) Optical images of 3D mesh structures printed using cell-
199 laden alginate and cell-laden collagen bioink. Live/dead images at 1 (left column) and 7 days (right
200 column) of the porous grid structure fabricated using the alginate and collagen bioinks containing the
201 osteoblast-like cells with more than 95% viability. Scale bar 300 μ m.(Kim, Yong Bok et al., 2016) D)
202 Stereomicroscopy 3D image of a gelatin methacrylamide-hyaluronic acid gel (GelMA-HA) and GelMA-
203 HA gel reinforced with a PCL scaffold (93% porosity) on day 1 (scale bars, 2 mm). Haematoxylin/eosin
204 staining (day 7) demonstrated chondrocytes in GelMA with a spherical morphology. Cells had a
205 homogenous distribution in the construct.(Visser et al., 2015) Reprinted with permission.

206
207 Despite the above mentioned recent progresses in the bioink development, the material used in 3D
208 Bioprinting is not the only parameter for the design of body organs and personalized medical devices.
209 The type of the 3D printer and the bioprinting processes should be addressed together with the bioinks.
210 This will require in near future personalized 3D printers, organ scanners and 3D computer models that
211 can be placed in operating rooms.

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214 **2.2 *In-vitro* fabrication of vascularized 3D tissue and organ constructs:**

215 Recent advances in 3D printing technology, microfabrication, and material sciences have facilitated the
216 use of bioprinting for engineering tissue constructs. For example, tissues such as cartilage(Markstedt et
217 al., 2015), skin(Binder et al., 2010), liver(Bhise et al., 2016), lung(Horváth et al., 2015), neuronal
218 tissue(Gu et al., 2016), and pancreas(Marchioli et al., 2015) have been engineered with precise
219 microarchitecture through bioprinting. Also, 3D bioprinting technique is applicable for fabrication of
220 tissues with a complex architecture such as heart valves(Duan et al., 2013). Compared to engineered
221 tissues fabricated through conventional methods, bioprinted constructs with uniform and controlled
222 distribution of cells and materials can exhibit higher cell viability and functionality(Kang et al., 2016).

223 One of the most critical implications of bioprinting in tissue engineering is to help improve the
224 vascularization of engineered tissue constructs. The viability of thick tissue constructs (greater than
225 1mm in thickness) depends on a strong vasculature network for diffusion of oxygen, nutrients and waste
226 products. Two recent bioprinting approaches explored engineering vascular networks within the
227 engineered tissue constructs through indirect bioprinting (Kolesky et al., 2014) and direct bioprinting
228 (Zhang et al., 2013). In the indirect bioprinting approach, a negative supportive mold is created initially,
229 which is then used to cast the desired polymer scaffold through a suitable drying method. Most often,
230 freeze-drying approach is used as it causes less shrinkage and can reproduce the designs accurately,
231 unlike critical-point drying approach. In case of the direct bioprinting approach, the scaffolds are
232 produced directly from the model material, through processes such as extrusion printing (Wang et al.,
233 2016). Similarly, for the fabrication of vasculatures, through the indirect bioprinting approach, a
234 'fugitive ink' (sacrificial and easily removable component), is used as bioink to print tubular networks
235 within the construct. For this approach, usually dissolvable or reversibly cross-linkable components such
236 as agarose or Pluronic are used, and channels are formed when the 'ink' is removed, which allows
237 infiltration of endothelial cells, eventually resulting in the formation of intricate vascular
238 networks(Dababneh and Ozbolat, 2014). These constructs can be maintained for extended periods of
239 time, and used for tissue engineering applications. In the latter direct bioprinting approach, cells are
240 printed bottom-up in a layer-by-layer fashion to form constructs with branched horizontal and vertical
241 tubes(Miller et al., 2012). Alternatively, a scaffold-free direct printing approach which prints cell
242 aggregates or spheroids that fuses over time to form larger tissues has also been investigated. Artificial
243 tissue constructs fabricated through direct bioprinting can be easily transitioned for implantation. Some
244 of the criteria to consider during fabrication are the ease of integration of these vascularized structures
245 with the native vascular network and maintenance of matching mechanical properties as that of the
246 native vessels(Shim et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2013). Both forms of printing, indirect and direct, have
247 their share of disadvantages and advantages. For instance, a wide range of biomaterials and bioinks,

248 including cells and bioactive agents can be used in the indirect 3D printing approach, but, the process is
249 complex and results in poorly organized final structures. In this regard, the direct bioprinting approach
250 allows for greater accuracy of spatial organization of the different materials. However, in this approach
251 the types of biomaterials that can be used are limited. Therefore, it is preferable to use a combination of
252 the two processes for printing complex structures through deposition of bioink and scaffold materials
253 (Kang et al., 2016) (Figure 2).

254 Figure 2. Modes and Applications of 3D Bioprinting A) A view of a generic bioprinter system at
255 different configurations (extrusion based) which can print on a substrate on a stage with a single or
256 multiple extruders B) Representative direct and indirect bioprinted structures. In direct bioprinting cell
257 containing base material is printed according to the designed 3D structure; in indirect bioprinting a
258 sacrificial level was removed to enable perfusable areas for providing nutrient and gas transfer for the
259 encapsulated cells in the bulk structure C) Representative drawings of the 4 most common bioprinting
260 methods, laser-based bioprinting, stereolithography droplet-based bioprinting and extrusion-based
261 bioprinting respectively D) Potential uses of bioprinting as i) artificial organs for diseased/damaged
262 organ/tissue replacement, ii) miniaturized organs for drug testing and disease models and iii) biorobots
263 for actuation, respectively.

264 **2.3 Tissue constructs for disease modeling and pharmaceuticals:**

265 In recent years, bioprinted tissue constructs have gained popular use in disease modeling and for drug
266 screening, as they can better recapitulate the native cell micro-niche *in vitro* (Ebrahimkhani et al., 2014).
267 Currently, researchers use either scaffold-based or scaffold-less approaches for developing models for
268 pharmaceutical testing and high throughput drug screening (Abdeen et al., 2016; Ebrahimkhani et al.,
269 2014). However, these models encounter several limitations from batch to batch variation and high
270 maintenance cost, to incorporating vascularization within the constructs. Hence bioprinted miniature
271 tissue models overcomes these limitations through precise deposition of cells and ECM constituents to
272 recapitulate the *in vivo* architecture (Rodríguez-Dévora et al., 2012). In addition, this technique provides
273 greater control over the size, cellular composition, vascularization and high throughput screening
274 capability. For instance, bioprinting processes such as thermal inkjet bioprinting have been used to print
275 *Escherichia coli*-laden alginate scaffolds for high throughput antibiotics screening (Rodríguez-Dévora
276 et al., 2012). One of the biggest advantages of bioprinted tissues is the capability to generate a vascular
277 network with capillary branches on multiple-scale, which facilitates the development of physiologically
278 relevant flow conditions for drug testing purposes. For example, Bhise et al., and Chang et al., used
279 extrusion-based bioprinting to develop 3D liver-on-a-chip model, to assess drug metabolic
280 properties (Bhise et al., 2016) and to test the hepatic toxicity of acetaminophen (Chang et al., 2010),
281 respectively. Such miniaturized model systems are also of interest for studies of drug metabolism in
282 space or in other planets and satellites for example for anti-radiation drugs (Chang et al., 2010; Snyder
283 et al., 2011). Such models can be made disease specific via development of tumor models for
284 comparative testing of chemotherapy agents which are more faithful than conventional 2D models in
285 3D printed format (Zhao et al., 2014).

286 Table 1 below summarizes the advantages, disadvantages and applications of the four main types of
287 bioprinting – droplet-based bioprinting, laser-based bioprinting, stereo-lithography (STL) and
288 extrusion-based bioprinting.

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298 **TABLE 1: Summary of advantages, disadvantages and applications of different bioprinting modalities.**

BIOPRINTING MODALITY	TISSUE TYPE	APPLICATION	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES	FUTURE NEEDS
Droplet-based printing (thermal based and piezoelectric based)	Cartilage tissue and cartilage defect repair, cardiac, liver, lung, vascular tissues and retinal ganglion cells.	High throughput drug-screening platform, cancer research and transplantation (Rodríguez-Dévora et al., 2012; Skardal et al., 2012; Xu et al., 2011)	High throughput (~10000 droplets/s), cost-effective, high precision printing, capable of creating gradients in scaffolds.	Frequent blockage of nozzle heads, Viability of cells and stability of proteins affected due to mechanical shear and thermal stress, limited to printing liquid materials.	Improve resolution for printing small channels or vessels, improve capability to print more complex structures
Extrusion based bioprinting	Blood vessels, heart, skin, liver vascular tissues and heterocellular tissue spheroids.	Bioprinted liver and high throughput cell arrays for pharmaceuticals and drug testing, breast and cervical cancer research. (Atala and Yoo, 2015; King, Shelby M et al., 2014)	Capability to print versatile types of materials of any geometry, high cell viability compared to inkjet printing, owing to operation at room temperature, capability to create homogenous distribution of cells	Low resolution and non-optimal (printing condition based) cell viability of final constructs, limited mechanical stiffness owing to use of hydrogels, difficulty in maintaining the shape of construct owing to mismatch between material density and the liquid medium.	Develop new biomaterials with better mechanical characteristics,

Stereolithography (STL)	Blood vessels, Cartilage, muscle-neuron co-cultures	Tissue engineer blood-vessels and cartilage, tissue models, engineered organ-on-a-chip devices. Engineer biomimetic scaffolds(Chan et al., 2010; Melchels et al., 2009; Zorlutuna et al., 2011)	Nozzle-free printing, very high resolution, high cell-viability (~90%), low cost and high printing speed (<40,000 m/s), capable of printing light-sensitive hydrogels.	Limited to photocurable polymers, lack of biodegradable and biocompatible biomaterials, toxic residual materials from photo-curing reagents, can cause harmful reactions and DNA damage.	Develop new biocompatible and biodegradable polymers. Develop visible light based STL systems.
Laser-assisted bioprinting	Vascular, heart, Bone, Skin.	Accurately control pore size, geometry and mechanical properties(Zopf et al., 2013)	High cell viability (>95%), precise delivery of cell laden ink droplets and high resolution, non-contact mode of printing.	High cost of set-up and operation, time consuming and prone to metallic particle contamination	Improve cytocompatibility of laser based techniques

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302 Bioprinted tissue constructs also enable the investigation of cell-cell and cell-matrix interactions in a
303 controlled, biomimetic microenvironment(Unger et al., 2014). This approach has widely been used for
304 developing various cancer tissue models and investigating various antitumor drugs(Knowlton et al.,
305 2015; Zervantonakis et al., 2012). In recent years, the use of 3D bioprinters for fabricating disease
306 models, especially for cancer drug screening has entered the commercial domain. Companies like
307 Organovo are actively developing 3D printed models for high throughput screening and have recently
308 demonstrated a scaffold-free human breast cancer model for pharmaceutical use(King, Shelby M. et al.,
309 2014).

310 However, beyond the highly controlled miniaturized models, the biomechanical properties and
311 biochemical composition of tissues and organs *in vivo* also needs to be considered for more clinical
312 applications. Matching the complex biomechanical and biochemical properties of various tissues and
313 printing them with high precision is very difficult; thus developing new tissues for transplant or
314 regeneration proves challenging. Successful transplantation and regeneration of tissues, especially those
315 of musculoskeletal origin such as cartilage and bone depend on the mechanical characteristics of the
316 bioprinted artificial tissues and scaffolds. The biomaterials used for the fabrication should have the
317 required physical characteristics for the printing process in order to match the properties of the native
318 tissue. Foremost, the ink used should be capable of providing sufficient strength and stiffness required
319 in the dynamic environment of the target tissue. Mainly, the physical characteristics of the biomaterial
320 used determines the printing type. For example, bioinks with low viscosity are usually printed through
321 inkjet printing. In case of hydrogels, although they can be tailored to create biomimetic niches, they
322 have low elastic modulus and are too soft to withstand physiological conditions of the musculoskeletal
323 tissues (Vedadghavami et al., 2017). Similarly, in case of cartilage tissues, a hybrid bioprinting method,
324 a combination of 3D bioprinting and electrospinning techniques, could prove optimal for fabricating
325 cartilage with improved mechanical properties. For instance, Xu et al., used a hybrid bioprinting
326 approach to fabricate cartilage tissue with enhanced mechanical properties(Xu et al., 2013). In general,
327 the biocompatibility and biomechanical properties of the printed scaffolds, depends on the scaffold
328 properties such as porosity, elasticity and stiffness.

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330 **2.4 *In situ* bioprinting of tissue constructs:**

331 One of the major applications of tissue engineered constructs is transplanting them to patients for
332 regenerative medicine purposes. However, the transplantation process is complex and has many
333 limitations such as poor donor-recipient compatibility, immune rejection of the transplant and poor
334 neovascularization after grafting. In addition, the size and shape of the artificially engineered tissue
335 constructs have to match the size of the defect *in vivo*, and incompatibility could prolong surgical timing.
336 Thus, directly bioprinting tissues and organs into the defect sites could help overcome some of the
337 drawbacks and facilitate rapid vascularization, reduce contamination and cost (Sengupta, D. et al., 2014;
338 Wang et al., 2015). Direct deposition of cells, genes, and cytokines inside the defect would facilitate
339 faster migration and regeneration of new tissue with the aid of native cells. Thus, *in situ* bioprinting has
340 been garnering considerable interest in recent years as an alternative to *in vitro* printing.

341 Currently, various proof-of-concept studies have shown the applicability of *in situ* bioprinting for
342 regenerating skin(Keriquel et al., 2010) and osteochondral tissues in mouse models(Cohen et al., 2010).
343 In one of the trials, amniotic fluid-derived stem cells, and bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells
344 were resuspended in fibrin-collagen gel and directly printed over the wound site using an inkjet
345 printer(Skardal et al., 2012). The encapsulated cells within the construct released chemical trophic
346 factors that promoted increased angiogenesis and wound closure. Similarly, *in vivo* repair of
347 osteochondral(Park et al., 2014) defects in the mouse has also been shown.

348 As seen from these various examples, bioprinting is a rapidly growing field that has revolutionized the
349 field of tissue engineering, regenerative medicine and disease modelling. However, there are still some
350 major bottlenecks. So far, *in situ* bioprinting is limited to printing superficial and easily accessible tissues
351 such as the skin. Printing of tissues internally is complicated with non-horizontal surfaces, high oxygen
352 and moisture conditions *in vivo*. This process requires rapidly cross-linkable, biocompatible bioinks for

353 fabrication. Therefore, transfer of bioprinting from the laboratory to a clinical setting is still in emerging
354 stage and requires simultaneous advances in biomaterial engineering, microfabrication, and surgical
355 technologies.

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357 **3. Advantages of 3D printing in surgical context**

358 3.1 Implantable 3D printed structures

359 The advantages of 3D printing can be divided into several categories. Those related to implantable
360 devices are based on personalization which will be helpful for non-standard size patients and pathology
361 related unique anatomical conditions. Moreover, 3D printing enables the development of
362 multicomponent structures with site specific physical and mechanical properties which is not achievable
363 with molding and potential temporal control over the implant properties when degradable materials are
364 used(Pokorny et al., 2017). This is particularly relevant, for example, in the field of craniofacial
365 reconstruction where the anatomical features to be replaced rarely conform to any standard and the
366 functional outcomes go hand in hand with aesthetic concerns. Formulations based on printable bioactive
367 glasses provide implants that are not only near perfect fits to the defect site (hence significantly
368 decreasing the operation time by obviating the need to reshape the implant to the defect; something that
369 needs to be done for autografts for example) but also provide a spatial control over the presence of
370 bioactive components which will facilitate the integration of the implant(Bergmann et al., 2010).
371 Incorporation of active components such as bioglass provides another level of opportunity to modify the
372 implants with respect to the patient's capacity to heal by adjusting the bioactive components without
373 interfering with the implant production process. In conventional implantable device design such subtle
374 modifications are neither easy to implement nor practiced regularly. However, such modifications can
375 only be done within the limit of printability conditions which is a function of the technique used(Eosoly
376 et al., 2012).

377 Another advantage of 3D printing is the reduction of the manufacturing steps of the products and their
378 fast delivery, which is very important for the reconstruction of cancers. In addition to this, 3D printed
379 organ models provide a haptic learning experience for the surgeons. In many cases, graspable 3D objects
380 are more useful compared to 3D visualization techniques for both training and surgical planning.
381 Currently, these are used in a case-by-case basis but just as 3D imaging techniques entered to the routine
382 use in surgical configurations in the context of image guided surgery, it is possible to envision the use
383 of 3D objects for planning and diagnosis in the near future particularly if the future technologies can
384 offer cheap, fast printing of the objects in situ. Moreover, use of 3D printing can also have a steering
385 effect on future imaging modalities as the post-processing of the images required for rapid prototyping.
386 One example of such techniques is Black Bone MRI which can decrease the contrast due to the
387 surrounding soft tissue (Eley et al., 2017). The use of 3D printed structures for diagnosis, planning and
388 treatment has demonstrated via such models more accurate diagnosis, better comprehension of the
389 pathological structures to be resected can be achieved. The potential benefits of such systems are
390 significant decreases in intra-operative complications and also decreased surgical time and cost (Rengier
391 et al., 2010).

392 As for implants, currently standardized uses of 3D printing surgery are development of custom made
393 craniofacial implants for reconstructive surgery purposes and also personalization of metal orthopedic
394 implants such as hip implants. In both cases, the event-specific nature of the defects creates a
395 disadvantage with the preformed implants as their fixation to the defect site would either require fillers
396 or removal of otherwise healthy tissue. However in these cases, the concern is mostly an anatomical fit
397 and 3D printing can provide advantages beyond just accurate placement.

398 One good example of such applications is non-standardized implants for pediatric patients. Importance
399 of elasticity and high precision conformity of the implanted material in a growing infant are crucial. For
400 example, tracheobronchomalacia can be a fatal problem in newborns due to the risk of airway collapse.
401 Due to the fact that, the features of the airway are under constant flux due to growth in such cases,
402 application of standard implants is not feasible. Surgical solutions to this problem has complication rates

403 as high as 40%. To overcome this, Zopf et al. (Zopf et al., 2013) used a custom bioresorbable (PCL
404 based) tracheal splint with a bellowed architecture (which creates extra resistance against collapse and
405 also extension while the infant is growing) . The implantation of the device decreased the carbon dioxide
406 partial pressure in venous blood significantly and after 21 days the child was cut off from ventilation
407 support and discharged. One-year follow-up confirmed a patent airway and the implant is expected to
408 be completely resorbed within 3 years. This is a good demonstration of how 3D printing technology can
409 provide an implant based solution where previously there was none possible. The same group continued
410 their work with 3 additional patients, all of which were free of tracheobronchomalacia related
411 complications after up to 2 years at the time of the reporting. Another group described the first case of
412 impassable complex tracheal stenosis in adult that was efficiently treated with a stent insertion guided
413 using a 3D printed model (Guibert et al., 2017). Biodegradation also provides pre-designed temporal
414 effects (sometimes referred, although not very accurately, as 4D printing together with other possible
415 means to control long term behavior of the printed structures). For example, controlled degradation as a
416 function of polymer properties and also physicochemical properties (porosity, wettability, roughness
417 etc.) can be engineered to match biological events such as wound healing in the surrounding tissues or
418 growth in the case of pediatric patients.

419 Tissue and organ replacement following cancer can also benefit from temporal effects. Recently our
420 group has reported the implantation of an artificial larynx device that can partially replace the functions
421 of a resected larynx up to 13 months (Debry et al., 2017). Such devices can also benefit from 3D printing
422 based modifications as the extent of tissue removal in laryngeal cancers is a function of affected tissue
423 area and patient-specific. Moreover, application of radio and/or chemotherapy as a safety measure also
424 has effects on the properties of the tissue around the resection zone; temporal, inducible changes would
425 provide a way to counteract the effects of such intervention on the success of implantable devices. The
426 advantage of having this level of flexibility with such devices was evident during the aforementioned
427 tracheal splints; in order to compensate for the presence of severe bronchomalacia in one of the patients;
428 the device design was slightly modified and overall the modification only took an additional 3
429 hours(Morrison et al., 2015a), while the whole process took 2-5 days for each patient.

430 In surgery, a major step for 3D printed parts that presents challenges is sterilization. The creation of
431 surgical guides, veneers, drill guides, and abutments require autoclaving for use. Most thermoplastics
432 that are widely used in biomedical applications, particularly polylactic acid (PLA) and polyglycolic acid
433 (PGA), will not survive a standard autoclave cycle (Neches et al., 2016; Rozema et al., 1991).
434 Sterilization with γ -radiation is effective, but causes drastic changes to the biochemical properties of
435 the material (Gilding et al., 1980). Some printed material can be sterilized by common methods as
436 autoclave, gamma or ethylene oxide such as polyetheretherketone (PEEK) and titanium. PEEK custom
437 implants were used to correct cranial, frontal and mandibular defects ((Parthasarathy, 2014).

438 For surgical devices, surgical planning and education; there are also distinct advantages of 3D printing.
439 For example, personalized intubation tubes can significantly decrease the side effects related to
440 intubation. A significant portion of complications arises from the incompatibility of the tubes with a
441 given patient's anatomy, which creates trauma, excessive inflammation, ischemia and tissue damage in
442 prolonged intubation period. This would be difficult to achieve in emergency conditions due to the delay
443 between imaging, reconstruction and printing; but for the case of intubation for anesthesia, it is easily
444 foreseeable.

445 **3.2 Diagnostic use of 3D printed Structures**

446 Beyond replacement, 3D printing also has diagnostic and evaluation value. There is certain aspects of
447 having a tangible object in hand that limits the restrictions of images even when they are in 3D, such as
448 imparting the properties of the target tissues organs (stiffness, texture, distinct differences in
449 physicochemical properties in different regions) that cannot be communicated with imaging alone. 3D
450 printed structures bring in a realistic haptic element to surgical training and planning. For example, some
451 surgical models have been developed for the demonstration and simulation of multiple hepatobiliary
452 interventions, for training purposes and patient counseling (Javan and Zeman, 2017). The overall
453 potential benefits will be better surgical outcomes, less post-surgery complications and significant
454 decreases in operation duration. For instance, a recent clinical example is the use of a 3D printed model

455 for evaluation of the upper airway of a laryngectomized patient(Han et al., 2016). The patient was going
456 to go under anesthesia for removal of a tumor in his pelvis. However, his prior laryngectomy with a
457 stenosis below the tracheostoma created difficulties for assessment of his airways for anesthesia
458 purposes. In order to be able to carry out an evaluation, the clinical team printed a 3D model of the
459 patient's trachea from poly-L-lactic acid based on CT images and made the pre-anesthesia planning with
460 the information obtained from the model (which showed a stenosis below stoma and retraction of the
461 stomal scar). Equipped with this information, the team practiced the intubation in the printed model and
462 did their planning accordingly (size and the location of the cannula). This resulted in a successful surgery
463 which would have been compromised had the conventional methods of analysis been used instead. As
464 intubation related complications is a leading cause of death in patients with multiple co-morbidities,
465 such preventive means can significantly decrease complication related patient loss.

466 The next challenge in such applications is the incorporation of relevant information beyond the
467 anatomical/pathological features such as mucosal inflammation or changes in biomechanical properties
468 within the modelled volume. Moreover, the ability to print multiple materials can provide models that
469 can surpass the level of information that can be gleaned from. For example, Wu et al. used a 3D printed
470 patient specific bone model (phantom) embedded in a hydrogel based transparent matrix which allows
471 the visualization of the hard tissue with its relation to the surrounding tissues which cannot be achieved
472 by a cadaver as the surrounding tissue is naturally opaque (Wu, Y.Y. et al., 2016) using clubfoot as a
473 demonstration . This model provides a means to teach the practitioners how to handle the clubfoot in
474 the presence of the surrounding soft tissue while being able to see the results of their interventions
475 through the transparent layer.

476 Another potential use of 3D printing is the creation of reverse models, such as wounds and similar tissue
477 defects. This is particularly important in surgeries such as free flap (where a donor tissue from patient's
478 own body is used to fill or reconstruct a compromised part of the body due to burns, infection, tumor
479 resection etc.) where surgical planning and surgical guides are crucial for minimizing the donor site
480 morbidity and flap ischemia time (Culie et al., 2016). For example, for mandibular reconstruction, 3D
481 printing provides a decisive contribution to this complex operation by allowing optimal planning on a
482 template, with a significant gain in operation time and improved quality of pre-conformed screw plates,
483 improved precision of the procedure and better fibula free flap survival by using cutting guides (Dupret-
484 Bories et al., 2017). Chae et al created a reverse model of a wound defect around an ankle prosthesis
485 with significant complications(Chae et al., 2015). In the end, because the prosthesis is exposed a salvage
486 operation with a volumetric filling of the defect with a free flap was decided. 3D reconstructions based
487 on computer tomographic angiography were used to obtain a negative defect model for pre-operative
488 preparation; the use of the 3D printed model resulted in a surgery with no complications and minimal
489 amount of tissue harvesting at the donor site.

490

491 Using 3D printing techniques, risk free surgical training on objects that are highly mimetic of natural
492 organs both from mechanical and architectural point of view, which can be used for interaction with
493 patients to achieve a better understanding and compliance for diseases that require surgery can be done.
494 This would lead to improved surgical planning and preparation based on the on spot printing of tumors,
495 or damaged tissues that can lead to better decision making and less complications. This is particularly
496 relevant for surgeries for conditions which are either rare or too complicated with respect to the ongoing
497 activities of the surgeons (such as organ defects or rare anatomical anomalies in newborns).
498 Establishment of highly representative training models will improve the success rates of rare surgeries
499 and also might lead to development of new surgical techniques too risky to be tried in-situ. Valverde et
500 al have objectively investigated the impact of 3D models on the surgical decision change of 40 patients
501 with complex congenital heart defects. In 19 of the 40 complex cases, consideration of a 3D model
502 redefined surgical management (Valverde et al., 2017). In another recent study, Komai et. al have
503 developed a 3D printed kidney for surgical navigation in minimally invasive off-clamp partial
504 nephrectomy (Komai et al., 2016).

505

506 **4. Biorobotics:**

507 Recently, advances in tissue engineering and microfabrication techniques have led to the development
508 of a new research field that explores the possibility of hybrid biological machines called
509 biorobots(Feinberg, 2015; Kim et al., 2013). These synthetic biological systems or devices are composed
510 of a soft biological component, such as living cells or muscle explants, incorporated into an artificial
511 mechanical support. Usually, elastomeric materials such as polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) or hydrogels
512 are used as the mechanical support system of the device(Majidi, 2014; Vogel, 2012). In comparison,
513 traditional robots are rigid systems made of materials with an elastic modulus greater than 1 MPa(Ricotti
514 and Mencias, 2012) and are limited in their range of motion. Biorobots have garnered tremendous
515 interest in recent years, and various studies have been carried out leading to the development of devices
516 that can grip(Tanaka et al., 2006), walk(Chan et al., 2012), pump(Park et al., 2007; Tanaka et al., 2007),
517 and swim(Herr and Dennis, 2004; Holley et al., 2016). These devices, inspired by locomotion in nature
518 and coupled with engineering design principles, are aimed to perform various biomimetic functions that
519 traditional robots are not capable of executing. In addition, these devices are environmentally safe as no
520 toxic byproduct is released during manufacturing or operation. They also have the potential self-healing
521 capacity, low electromechanical footprint and can be self-sufficient in their energy needs. The cells can
522 generate sufficient power to drive the device through the breakdown of nutrients that could be absorbed
523 from their microenvironment, thus eliminating the need for mechanically driven energy supply.

524 However, these biorobotic devices have one major drawback. Since they are based solely on the
525 contractile activity of the cells, motion control and reliable operation of these devices remains a
526 challenge. Recent studies have shown that these drawbacks can be overcome by using electrical field
527 stimulation to direct the rate of cell contraction(Feinberg et al., 2007) or using genetically engineered
528 cells that are responsive to light to control the direction of movement(Park et al., 2016; Raman et al.,
529 2016). Few other studies have been investigating the potential of incorporating neuromuscular junctions
530 within the tissue constructs(Langhammer et al., 2011), which could be then selectively stimulated to
531 guide device movement. In addition, some recent studies are exploring the potential of developing cell-
532 based computing devices that function as logic gates and diodes using neurons(Feinerman et al., 2008)
533 and muscle cells(Can et al., 2017). Such biocomputing devices can be incorporated with the biorobots
534 and could be used as control units for the biorobots.

535 In this section, we will first discuss current approaches for fabricating biological actuators that can be
536 used in biorobotics applications, and then review the current state of micro and macro-scale stand-alone
537 biorobots, with particular discussion on how 3D bioprinting technologies can help fasten the progress
538 in this emerging field of bioengineering.

539 **4.1 Biological actuators:**

540 Actuation is a ubiquitous function for any machine or biological system that undergoes movement and
541 interacts with the surrounding environment. Within the biological system, molecular motors form the
542 functional building blocks, guiding motility over a wide range of length scales. These protein machines
543 operate by converting chemical energy, available as adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and guanine
544 triphosphate (GTP), into work(Mallik and Gross, 2004), guiding or driving diverse functions from cell
545 division, transcription to muscle contraction. Combined with other feedback control signals, they can
546 operate in scalable temporal, spatial and force regimes; however, these operations are difficult to realize
547 synthetically(Sengupta, S. et al., 2014; Sweeney and Houdusse, 2010). Hence, biorobots that incorporate
548 molecular motor actuator systems with multiscale designs to engineering dynamic hybrid systems are
549 naturally superior in functionality to traditional synthetic actuators.

550 In addition to biorobots that are solely driven by molecular actuators(Hess, 2011), cell-based biological
551 actuators are used in larger devices to generate the required force for device function. These actuators
552 are typically composed of contractile cells cultured as a confluent layer on a thin, flexible
553 substrate(Alford et al., 2010; Xi et al., 2005). Synchronous and rhythmic contraction of the cells exerts
554 considerable stress on the substrate, causing it to bend, resulting in actuation. Mammalian cardiac and
555 skeletal muscle cells are predominantly the types of cells used for biorobot actuation(Alford et al., 2010).
556 Smooth muscles exhibit low tonic contractions below the minimum threshold of 0.5 Hz needed to

557 generate sufficient power(Ricotti and Menciassi, 2012) and hence are not commonly used. On the other
558 hand, mammalian muscle cells that exhibit rhythmic contractions of 1 Hz are easily susceptible to
559 temperature changes (greater or lesser than 37°). As an alternative, contractile insect cells specifically
560 cells from dorsal vessel tissue can be used to aid the operation of biological actuators. These cells have
561 long-term viability at atmospheric temperature and can be easily engineered to survive low nutrient
562 conditions, extreme temperature, and pH conditions(Akiyama et al., 2009; Akiyama et al., 2013).

563 One of the earliest silicon-based bioactuators was used as biosensors, as the toxins in the
564 microenvironment can influence the cell contractility (or cantilever deflection)(Xi et al., 2005).
565 Similarly, this principle of deflection of the cantilever beam (or micropillars in the case of surface bound
566 cantilever array), in proportion to forces exerted by the cells, can be utilized to determine the contractile
567 strength of many cells(Akiyama et al., 2009; Tanaka et al., 2006). They also represent the change in
568 contractile and traction forces the cells exert as they mature or differentiate over time(Holley et al.,
569 2016). Free standing contractile cell sheets can be fabricated by seeding the cells on a thin carrier film,
570 resulting in muscular thin films (MTF)(Feinberg et al., 2007). The MTFs can either act independently
571 as mobile actuators, or can further be developed into devices that can function as a swimmers, grippers,
572 and walkers.

573 **4.2 Micro to macro scale biorobots:**

574 Recent years has seen an increased application of 3D printed scaffolds for fabrication of transplantable
575 tissue patches and cells for tissue and organ regeneration. Furthermore, 3D printing techniques have
576 been adapted to directly bioprint tissues and organs as discussed in the other section in this review article.
577 In addition to these applications, there is a demand for small, biocompatible robotic devices that can
578 perform functions like tissue repair, cargo transport or drug delivery efficiently. These 3D-printed
579 biorobots can also be used to better understand the locomotive mechanism of small-scale
580 microorganisms and swimmers as seen in the work by Nawroth *et al.*, where a biohybrid microrobot
581 mimicking the motility of spermatozoa was developed.

582 Over the years, biorobots of different dimensions and functionality, based on molecular motors for
583 actuation, have been developed. These biorobots vary from micro- to macro-scale (10^{-9} – 10^2 m) in size.
584 At single cellular level, prokaryotes such as bacteria(González et al., 2014; Peyer et al., 2013), are highly
585 adaptable and have been harnessed to perform multiple functions ranging from the formation of a
586 collective unit to drive submillimeter gears(Sokolov et al., 2009), to package delivery guided by a
587 chemical gradient(Kim et al., 2012). At a larger scale, muscle powered actuators based biorobots that
588 can perform complex functions have been developed.

589 Each of these multiple devices has a unique engineered design, that is partly or entirely inspired by the
590 native biological systems coupled with novel engineering principles. For example, Williams *et al.*,
591 developed a simple cardiomyocyte and PDMS based swimming biorobot that exhibited flagella-based
592 propulsion, to model spermatozoa(Williams et al., 2014)⁵. The device has a long, flexible PDMS tail
593 (flagellum) attached to a short head. Propulsion is triggered by the passive deflection of the flagellum
594 in response to the spontaneous contraction of cardiomyocytes seeded at the base of the head. Similarly,
595 other swimming devices based on jet-propulsion, modeled on a jellyfish and fin-based
596 propulsion(Nawroth et al., 2012), based on ostraciiform swimmers have been developed(Holley et al.,
597 2016). The body of the fin-based propulsion device has the unique capability of self-stabilization. To
598 achieve this, two modified PDMS composites (PDMS mixed with either microballoons or nickel), with
599 different densities is used as the base with a cardiac cell MTF as the cantilever (fin)(Holley et al., 2016).
600 Likewise, the frame of the jet-propulsion based biorobot developed by Nawroth *et al.* was fabricated to
601 accurately model the jellyfish, including anisotropic alignment of cardiomyocytes to mimic the *in vivo*
602 structure(Nawroth et al., 2012).

603 However, some of the earliest muscle cell-based devices were more simplistic and were developed as a
604 micro-pump, to control the direction of flow within a microchannel(Trumble, 2002). The micropump
605 consisted of cardiomyocytes seeded as a thin film on a dome-shaped PDMS membrane. Spontaneous
606 contractions of the cells caused pulsatile motion of the membrane, thereby acting as a diaphragm which

607 directed the fluid flow within the microchannel(Tanaka et al., 2007). Various other micromechanical
608 systems based on muscle cells integrated with artificial micro-parts that are capable of manipulating
609 other single cells have also been developed to function as micro- tweezers and grippers. These biorobots
610 paved the way for fabricating more complex devices. For instance, Chan *et al.*, used the 3D printing
611 technique, stereolithography, to fabricate an asymmetric multi-material biorobot, consisting of the
612 biological “biomorph” cantilever structure seeded with cardiomyocytes as the actuator(Chan et al.,
613 2012), that can function as a walking biorobot (Figure3).

614 Although, the functional aspect of these biorobots is purely speculative, they could be integrated with
615 sensors that are capable of detecting the presence of toxins in the environment, so it can follow along a
616 toxin gradient and deliver antitoxins. In addition, these devices have great potential to be a part of
617 artificial immune systems in the future. With further development of the biomaterials used for their
618 fabrication, these devices can be tailored to carry payloads such as, encapsulated cells, drugs and
619 tracking devices. The later would facilitate researchers to track the device throughout its trajectory. For
620 example, such devices could potentially be developed further, miniaturized and used to detect and
621 remove blockages in the human gut.

622 The function of these biorobots can be improved by introducing anisotropic alignment to increase the
623 contraction force generated by the cells(Feinberg et al., 2007), electrical stimulation to control the rate
624 of contraction or incorporating genetically engineered, light responsive cells to guide the direction of
625 motion. Recently combining tissue engineering and optogenetics, Park *et al.*, developed a unique
626 swimming biorobot modeled on an electric sting ray(Park et al., 2016), with anisotropically patterned
627 cardiac cells and PDMS body enclosing a gold cytoskeleton. The swimming direction of this biorobot
628 was guided by a blue LED light, and they were capable of traversing a distance of 1.5 mm per second.
629 Cvetkovic et al. used 3D printing for C2C12 skeletal muscle myoblast powered micromachines using
630 Matrigel and other ECM molecules as bioinks(Cvetkovic et al., 2014) .

631

632 Figure 3: (A) Diagram of 3D stereo-lithographic printer (B) Process flow diagram for biobot fabrication.
633 (C) Fabricated bio-bots (cantilever and base). (D) Collagen functionalization of the cantilevers and
634 cardiac cell incorporation (E) Cross-sectional images of iterative bio-bot designs (F) Final bio-bot design
635 (G) Bio-bots after cardiac cell seeding (day 3) on the cantilever side facing the base. Cantilever curls
636 due to the tension created by cell cytoskeleton. Scale bars: 1 mm. Reprinted with permission from Nature
637 Publishing Group.

638 Despite the recent developments, the field of biorobotics is still in its growing phase, encumbered with
639 challenges. An individual cell is capable of synthesizing, assembling and packaging molecular motors
640 and delivering them to target sites or form larger scale contractile units. However, macroscale assembly
641 of molecular motors synthetically, *in vitro* is complex and with the current technology, limited by the
642 high cost of manufacture and low supply source(Hess, 2011). In addition, the long-term viability of
643 these devices remains a challenge as the bacteria-based devices have a very short life cycle, and muscle
644 cells-based devices require stringent conditions for viability. However, currently developed engineering
645 approaches for fabricating the various biorobots being investigated have great potential to pave the way
646 for the development of more robust devices with a broader range of practical applications especially for
647 advancing medical procedures. For instance, 3D printing techniques facilitate the fabrication of complex
648 miniaturized systems by combining different materials (synthetic and biological), with different
649 properties. Use of 3D bioprinting for the fabrication of biorobots enables the researchers to easily design,
650 fine-tune and develop these devices to perform efficiently *in vitro* and *in vivo* with improved motility
651 for various biomedical applications.(Stanton et al., 2015)

652

653 There are many tissue engineering and fabrication techniques available for engineering biomimetic cell
654 culture environments as well as biorobots *in vitro*, but 3D-printing based manufacturing makes the
655 process easier, reduces the cost and minimizes the consumption of reagents.

656 **5. Future directions:**

657 For medical applications two important challenges still remain for 3D printing. First one is the
658 heterogeneous nature of the tissues that contain composites of multiple materials with distinct
659 physicochemical properties. Thus, for implantable structures and bioprinting, it is desirable to have
660 simultaneous printing of multiple materials which is not a trivial problem. Recently, Liu et al. reported
661 multimaterial extrusion printing using a digitally controlled printhead(Liu et al., 2017). The printhead
662 comprises 7 capillary structures that can be used to print multicomponent structures using coded bioinks
663 (Figure 4A). The system was used to print various shear thinning bioinks and also conductive bioinks
664 for bioelectronics applications. The second challenge is the fact that the material microenvironment of
665 cells is highly stimuli responsive in the physiological conditions. In order to mimic this property, stimuli
666 responsive bioinks under printing conditions that incorporated physical stimuli (such as electric field)
667 are also under development(Yang et al., 2017) (Figure 4B). In both cases precision and quality of
668 multimaterial printing together with considerations related to in-situ bioprinting such as prevention of
669 contamination during printing are long-term questions that needs to be tackled. A recent study Li et al.
670 demonstrated the feasibility of on-site printing of implantable materials for the case of anterior cruciate
671 ligament; where specific implants were printed with a desktop printer from PLA and implanted in
672 defects in rabbits.

673
674

675 **Figure 4.** Bioprinting of Multimaterial 3D constructs. A,B) Stacks C–E) Co-centric vessel-like
676 structures F) A multicomponent pyramid. G,H) Layered blocks with continuous segments I)
677 Miniaturized organ mocks. Reprinted with permission from [100] J) Printing of Multiwalled Carbon
678 Nanotube enriched polymers under electric field for controlling the mechanical properties of the final
679 structures. Reprinted with permission from [101].

680

681 Another challenge is the high precision modification of 3D printed surfaces in complex configurations
682 and gradients. This is required for incorporation of smart and reactive components in implantable
683 devices, establishing necessary structural complexity and spatial control in applications such as
684 biocomputing and soft robotics. However, due to the disruptive nature of 3D printing technology special
685 attention must be given to the required steps for the adoption of the developed systems either at clinical
686 level or at industrial level. A recent technology adoption analysis (Steenhuis, 2016) shows that despite
687 the large body of technological advances the actual application of 3D printed structures in regular
688 clinical use is highly limited. However, the level of standardization of Additive Manufacturing
689 techniques in other fields such as Aerospace and Automotive industries provides a positive outlook for
690 more widespread adoption of current and future 3D printing techniques for medical applications. For
691 more advanced technologies such as bioprinting logistic considerations goes hand in hand with the
692 technological development such as the biopreservation of bioprinted organs; where there are significant
693 recent advances (Giwa et al., 2017). Thus, while additive manufacturing technologies provide a toolbox
694 for many fields, their success in personalized medicine will require tapping into the other tools provided
695 by different fields to harness its advantages. For example the advances in the pharmaceutical uses of 3D
696 printing (printing of personalized, on demand drugs with complex geometries to control drug release
697 rates) can drive the potential ‘precision functionalization” of 3D printed implants and tissue engineering
698 scaffolds (Norman et al., 2017). Similarly, although the 3D printed biorobots are currently in the early
699 stages of their development, with continuous development in fabrication techniques, these devices have
700 great potential for clinical application in the future, from delivery of drugs to *in vivo* screening
701 applications. The technologies described above pave the way for smart, responsive and customized
702 implants, engineered tissues and *in vivo* diagnostic tools (in the form of biorobots) which can resolve
703 many costly, life-threatening medical conditions.

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